

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: JOHNSON****FIRST NAME: HANNAH****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics
The author did use Zotero to insert references
The author did use Grammarly Premium
My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%
The author used the following software: MS Word for O365 on Windows 11

Key concepts:

1. Starting the Essay
2. Logical Flow
3. Editing the Essay
4. Style Guide
5. Plagiarism

ACADEMIC PAPER WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Period 1 of International Academic Writing (ACA-401) establishes a writing baseline for students pursuing a doctoral degree at Euclid University. It has been thirteen years since my master's degree was obtained using UK English, so this learning period was important to refresh my muscle memory related to academic writing. In this period, supported by the *ACA-401 Coursepack (Coursepack)*, I reminded myself of the core components of successful academic essay writing from how to start the article, establishing a logical flow of thought, editing the essay, utilizing Euclid's preferred style, and ways to avoid plagiarism. This response paper will focus on those five components to illustrate my understanding of the concepts.

2) STARTING THE ESSAY

When starting to write an essay, the *Coursepack* suggests drafting a plan before researching. This methodology has worked well for me in my work supporting various levels of government organizations, though I did not always make time for this during my earlier academic career. I learned the importance of writing for my job because I did not always prioritize this during my bachelor's degree. Drafting a plan enables me to ensure

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that I am telling a straightforward story to my reader, transitioning from one idea to the next as smoothly as possible. This plan informs the direction needed to research.

When researching, it is essential to mark areas for future exploration or reference within the essay. This is particularly important when inserting proper in-text citations, as the page number is required within these. Further, when marking areas for future exploration, it is essential to mark concepts that agree with your thesis statement and those that contradict it. “Do not only include evidence that agrees with what you are arguing; if there are different or opposing views, then they need to be examined” (Gulma and Cleenewerck 2021, 9). If you present a topic without contradiction, you leave your reader wondering about your thoughts on the contradiction and whether you have analyzed it thoroughly enough to warrant their reading time.

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3) LOGICAL FLOW

While the logical flow section of the course pack was short, I interpreted it as the beginning of understanding the style guide and a reinforcement of the need for establishing a good outline or plan during the starting phase. I appreciate the university templates, which include pre-determined styles and headers. I have used MS Word styles extensively in my career. I have found them incredibly helpful to keep the reader engaged and reinforce the author’s purpose across a paper and from a navigational standpoint. I enjoy using the Navigation bar to quickly jump to a specific document section, especially when ensuring clear transitions between paragraphs and paragraphs.

The *Coursepack* suggested that students learn to use adverbial phrases (e.g., “however,” “nonetheless”) to connect relationships within a paper. This will be a unique challenge for me as the audiences I have been writing for in the last decade (professionally) did not like these phrases. To assist me in overcoming this brain muscle memory, I have established a list of nuances for academic writing. I will use that list as part of my editing process.

4) EDITING THE ESSAY

Editing an essay is one of my favorite parts of writing. I wait a few days after completing my draft to ensure I can “think further about your answer and arguments and return to your essay with a fresh perspective” (Gulma and Cleenewerck 2021, 11). Then I use a multi-step methodology that is scoped to the appropriate level for the paper. The *Coursepack* provides a checklist of six critical questions to ask yourself, which support the process I have used since high school. I prefer to read my essay once for each area of review focus. My first read generally focuses on the critical question, “Does this argument make sense?” (Gulma and Cleenewerck 2021, 12). If the answer is no, I must go back to my initial plan to discover what went wrong. However, if the answer is yes, I typically prefer to next read the paper with an eye toward another critical question: evidential support. Does my evidence provide a tangible link to my thesis? Does it effectively counter any

contradictory arguments? Finally, I review for style last. I do this because the first two reviews will likely change my references, and I find I can save time by doing that review later.

One challenge I encountered during this response paper in the editing phase was learning to utilize Grammarly. I did not have access to Grammarly or anything like it during my bachelor's or master's study, nor [did](#) any of the writing I have done professionally. I found it to feel almost aggressive in its suggestions, so I may make a conscious decision to do my edits first rather than occasionally reviewing the Grammarly number on the screen. I believe establishing processes related to editing which best fit a person's preferences, so long as they utilize all the tools available, is important to the learning process.

5) STYLE GUIDE

My last editing step, reviewing for style, requires a strong understanding of a style guide and how to ensure you are following it appropriately. I appreciate style guides because they provide consistency across a piece of writing. As a reader, it can be challenging when an author changes their layout, font, spelling, or other core components of writing.

[EUCLID](#), uses the Chicago style, also referred to as Turabian. I was curious about why the two different names, so I turned to the Chicago Manual of Style website. There I learned the differences between the two styles and about the new ninth edition's focus on "building informational literacy, recognizing that most students will be doing their work largely or entirely online and on screens." (The University of Chicago Press, [n.d.](#)).

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6) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is an avoidable, serious offense, especially in academia. This period introduced many new (to me) tools that can aid in ensuring proper citations to provide credit to original thought appropriately. Zotero is a tool that I would have loved to use for my [master's](#) thesis work. I have downloaded the program, the internet, and MS Word extensions and found them extremely handy. I have also downloaded Grammarly's MS Word and browser extensions and found them helpful but risky. When reviewing Grammarly's suggested changes, I noticed several which changed the intent of the sentence. This illustrates the need for conscious editing.

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The *Coursepack* provided guidance on how to paraphrase ethically. Paraphrasing is not something I have ever been taught to do, and I appreciated one specific piece of guidance from the document: "the writing style you use to express the author's ideas must be different from the style the author used" (Gulma and Cleenewerck 2021, 36). An example that puts that advice into practice is the topic sentence of the paragraph above: "Plagiarism is an avoidable, serious offense, especially in academia." I wrote that sentence because I wanted to highlight the ability to avoid given the tools we have access to, but I

was also inspired by this from the *Coursepack*: "...[plagiarism] is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences" (Gulma and Cleenewerck 2021, 34).

7) CONCLUSION

This response paper explored the academic writing process for Euclid University. I can move forward with future response papers and longer products with the structure recommended within this period's *Coursepack*, from how to start effectively to producing logical flow, editing, and following the university style guide (with assistance from Zotero and Grammarly), and taking necessary steps to avoid plagiarism. These steps provide me with a strong foundation for future studies.

REFERENCES

- [Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru](#), 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.
- The University of Chicago Press. n.d. "Turabian: A Manual for Writers." Accessed September 24, 2022. <https://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org/turabian.html>.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.